

1 **Title:** Viral and Host Biomarkers of HIV Remission Post Treatment Interruption

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16

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24 **ABSTRACT:**

25 *Purpose of review:* HIV rebound/remission after antiretroviral therapy (ART) interruption is likely
26 influenced by (a) the size of the inducible replication-competent HIV reservoir and (b) factors in the host
27 environment that influence immunological pressures on this reservoir. Identifying viral and/or host
28 biomarkers of HIV rebound after ART cessation may improve the safety of treatment interruptions and
29 our understanding of how the viral-host interplay results in post-treatment control. Here we review the
30 predictive and functional significance of recently suggested viral and host biomarkers of time to viral
31 rebound and post-treatment control following ART interruption.

32

33 *Recent findings:* There are currently no validated viral or host biomarkers of viral rebound; however,
34 several biomarkers have been recently suggested.

35

36 *Summary:* A combination of viral and host factors will likely be needed to predict viral rebound and to
37 better understand the mechanisms contributing to post-treatment control of HIV, critical steps to
38 developing a cure for HIV infection.

39

40 INTRODUCTION

41 **I. The need for and challenges in identifying biomarkers of HIV rebound/remission post-treatment** 42 **interruption.**

43 Antiretroviral therapy (ART) effectively suppresses HIV replication in viremic individuals; however, the
44 establishment of persistent HIV reservoirs in blood and tissues prevents the eradication of the infection
45 [1-3]. In the vast majority of people living with HIV, HIV rebounds within a few weeks of interrupting
46 ART [4, 5], making life-long therapy a necessity. However, a few individuals (termed post-treatment
47 controllers, or PTCs) maintain viral remission for several months or years after stopping ART, through
48 unclear mechanism(s) [6]. Currently, there are no validated viral or host biomarker(s) that can predict the
49 time to viral rebound (TTVR) or the probability of viral rebound/remission upon ART cessation.

50

51 There are two main reasons that biomarkers of TTVR are needed. First, several curative interventions are
52 currently being tested in clinical trials [7, 4]. These trials rely on interrupting ART for determining the
53 efficacy of the tested intervention. These analytic treatment interruptions (ATIs) may pose risks to the
54 participants and the community [8]. Identifying a set of biomarkers that can be measured before ART
55 cessation and that predict the duration of remission and the probability of viral rebound could impact the
56 design and improve the safety of these clinical trials. These markers could allow for the selection of
57 individuals with a low risk of viral rebound to engage in ATIs. Second, identifying such viral and host
58 markers can provide the field with clues about the viral-host interactions that govern HIV persistence and
59 reactivation during and after ART cessation. These clues could be used to design novel interventions to
60 prevent viral rebound upon ART interruption.

61

62 Identifying biomarkers of TTVR or of the PTC phenotype has been complicated by several factors. First,
63 studies have been inconsistent regarding: 1) which value was used as the viral load threshold for defining
64 TTVR (e.g., time to 50 copies/ml, 200 copies/ml, 400 copies/ml, and/or 1000 copies/ml); 2) the type of
65 cells assayed; and 3) assay criteria, as described below. Second, studies that included PTCs have been
66 inconsistent regarding how they defined the PTC phenotype, e.g., in terms of duration of viral remission
67 and viral load thresholds [9, 10, 6, 11, 12]. Third, most studies have focused on viral measurements and
68 have largely ignored host factors that might contribute to post-treatment control.

69

70 Viral rebound is likely influenced by a combination of (a) the size of the inducible replication-competent
71 HIV reservoir and (b) factors in the host environment that influence immunological and inflammatory

72 pressures on this reservoir [4]. A combination of viral and host biomarkers will likely be needed to predict
73 viral rebound and to better understand how viral-host interactions control the likelihood that HIV will
74 rebound after ART cessation. In this article, we will start by reviewing proposed virological biomarkers
75 of TTVR and the likelihood of achieving a PTC phenotype upon ART cessation. We then review proposed
76 host biomarkers. We conclude by discussing how combining several types of biomarkers may enable us
77 to better predict and understand HIV rebound following treatment interruption.

78

79 **II. Viral biomarkers of time-to-viral-rebound and post-treatment control of HIV**

80 There is no consensus on a virological measurement that can estimate the full body burden of HIV
81 reservoirs during ART. There are several reasons for this lack of consensus (reviewed in detail in [4]).
82 First, the proportion of cells that are HIV-infected during suppressive ART is very small. Second, most of
83 these HIV-infected cells reside in multiple tissue compartments, not in blood [13-15]. Acquiring samples
84 from multiple tissues is challenging and prone to sampling biases. Third, there is no consensus on what
85 cell type can and should be used for these measurements (total CD4⁺ T cells, resting CD4⁺ T cells,
86 follicular helper CD4⁺ T cells, other subsets of CD4⁺ T cells, and/or other cell types such as myeloid cells)
87 [16-21]. Last, measurements evaluate different steps in the viral replication cycle and can depend on an
88 *ex vivo* stimulation step, complicating the interpretation of the measurements. Despite these important
89 caveats, most proposed biomarkers provide information about the disease process and may be useful in a
90 multi-component biomarker. In this section, we review several virological measurements that have been
91 associated with TTVR and/or probability of viral rebound/remission after ART interruption (**Table 1**).
92 We shall start by considering total and integrated proviral DNA, then intact proviral DNA and its
93 integration sites, followed by transcriptionally-active and translationally-active reservoirs, and ending
94 with the replication-competent reservoir. We shall also discuss measurement of residual plasma viremia,
95 as well as different clinical parameters that can affect both the size of HIV reservoirs and the potential
96 links between this size and viral rebound after ART cessation

97

98 *Total and integrated HIV DNA:* The quantity of total and integrated HIV DNA can be determined by PCR
99 amplification methods [e.g., quantitative PCR (qPCR) and droplet digital PCR (ddPCR)]. However, the
100 interpretation of these measures is complicated as most of the proviral DNA reservoir harbors mutations
101 and deletions that render it defective [22, 23, 15]. As a consequence, these assays overestimate the size of
102 replication-competent reservoirs. Despite this limitation, the pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA have been
103 associated with TTVR [12, 24, 25] as well as with post-treatment control [26, 11, 27, 25, 28, 29]. However,
104 such associations have not been consistent. In several other studies, levels of total HIV DNA did not

105 predict TTVR [30-33, 10]. The source of this discrepancy is not clear; however, it could be related to the
106 parameters used in determining TTVR, e.g., choices for viral load cutoff (at 50, 200, 400, or 1000
107 copies/ml) or levels of HIV DNA (e.g., the type of cells assayed, the region of HIV genome amplified,
108 and/or HIV sequence variability; **Table 1**). This discrepancy underscores the need to standardize the
109 parameters to determine TTVR and levels of HIV DNA so that the biological value of this simple
110 measurement can be better evaluated.

111

112 *Intact proviral HIV DNA:* Several methods have been used to estimate the levels of intact proviral DNA.
113 Proviral DNA sequencing can identify the frequency of intact and defective proviral species [22, 15, 34,
114 35]. Given the complexity of this measurement, its associations with TTVR or viral remission have not
115 been evaluated frequently. However, one recent study found that lower levels of defective and
116 hypermutated, but not intact, HIV DNA associated with delayed viral rebound [25]. In the same study, the
117 lower levels of intact, defective, and hypermutated HIV DNA were associated with a higher likelihood of
118 achieving a PTC phenotype after ATI [25]. The lack of observed correlation between intact HIV DNA
119 (measured by sequencing) and TTVR could be explained by the lower values and dynamic range of intact
120 HIV DNA levels (compared to defective and hypermutated HIV DNA levels). Newer assays have also
121 been implemented to distinguish between intact and defective proviruses, including the intact proviral
122 DNA assay (IPDA) [23], and the Quadruplex qPCR (Q4PCR) assay [36]. Two recent studies using IPDA
123 to measure intact HIV DNA found that lower levels of pre-ATI intact HIV DNA predicted delayed viral
124 rebound. The first study was a clinical trial investigating the effects of vesatolimod (a Toll-like Receptor
125 7 agonist) on viral rebound in HIV virological controllers [37] and the second study was performed in
126 patients treated during the chronic stage of HIV infection without interventions (abstract [38]). In addition,
127 PTCs have lower levels of intact HIV DNA, measured by IPDA, compared to post-treatment non-
128 controllers (abstract [39]). However, extensive investigations are still needed to examine whether intact
129 proviral HIV DNA levels in the blood and/or tissues, measured by IPDA or Q4PCR, correlate with the
130 time or probability of viral rebound/remission during ATIs.

131

132 *HIV proviral integration sites:* HIV proviral DNA integration site analysis can help predict the likelihood
133 of provirus inducibility. The integration of intact HIV proviral DNA into centromeric satellite regions has
134 been associated with the natural control of HIV [40, 41], and possibly the post-ART control of HIV
135 (abstract [42]). The longer durations of ART are associated with an enrichment of intact proviral DNA
136 integrated into centromeric satellite regions compared to proviral DNA integrated into transcriptionally
137 active sites [43]. This latter observation is compatible with a study found that a longer duration on ART

138 associated with a greater chance of post-treatment control [44] and suggests the presence of host
139 immunological pressures that target the inducible reservoir over time. These data suggest that
140 understanding the transcriptional activity of HIV integration sites may be key to predicting post-ART
141 control of HIV. However, such analyses (using MIP-seq [45] or PRIP-seq [43]) require a large number of
142 cells and are cost and labor-intensive. Therefore, it is unlikely that such analyses can be performed on a
143 large scale and more likely that they will be used to analyze a small number of individuals who, by other
144 measures, have already been determined to have a high probability of achieving ART-free control of HIV.

145

146 *Cell-associated HIV RNA:* Different cell-associated HIV transcripts (e.g., total, elongated, unspliced,
147 polyadenylated, and multi-spliced) can be quantified by qPCR and ddPCR methods. Although these
148 measures overestimate the size of the replication-competent reservoir [22, 23, 15], there is strong evidence
149 from multiple studies that their levels pre-ATI can predict TTVR ([10, 25, 33] and abstract [38]). Lower
150 pre-ATI levels of unspliced and multispliced HIV RNA, measured in PBMCs, have also been shown to
151 associate with post-treatment control of HIV [28, 25]. However, the association between HIV RNA and
152 TTVR is not consistent across studies [24, 31], likely because of the factors already noted above plus the
153 fact that the type of HIV transcripts measured by qPCR or ddPCR methods varies from study to study
154 [33]. [ENREF 10](#) [ENREF 12](#) The frequency of cells harboring transcriptionally active HIV can also be
155 measured using methods such as the Tat/Rev Induced Limiting Dilution Assay (TILDA) [46] and an *in*
156 *vitro* viral release assay [31]. Though there are limited data on whether these measures associate with
157 TTVR or the PTC phenotype, TTVR was not predicted by the viral release assay in one study [31]. Since
158 the level of different HIV transcripts is likely influenced by different host mechanisms [47], it will be
159 important to ascertain the interplay between these mechanisms and transcriptionally-active HIV reservoirs
160 that may contribute to viral rebound after ATI.

161

162 *Cell-associated HIV antigen:* The quantity of viral antigen (p24) in HIV-infected cells, in the absence or
163 presence of CD4⁺ T cell stimulation, can be measured using several digital immunoassays [48, 49].
164 Although this measure is likely reflects a more genetically intact HIV compared to total HIV DNA or cell-
165 associated RNA measures, it still overestimates the size of the replication-competent reservoir [50,
166 15] [ENREF 19](#). Unexpectedly, a recent clinical trial, which investigating the impact of pegylated
167 interferon α -2b (peg-IFN α -2b) monotherapy on HIV reservoir size and rebound after ATI, identified an
168 association between higher pre-ATI levels of *ex vivo* inducible cell-associated HIV p24 and a longer
169 TTVR after ATI (abstract [51]). What underlies this counterintuitive association is not clear, though it is
170 possible that the inducibility of HIV reservoirs to produce viral antigen might prime the innate immune

171 system (stimulated by IFN) to control the rebound-competent virus after ART cessation. The links
172 between p24 measurements (with and without stimulation), antigen/antibody-mediated innate immune
173 functions, immune activation, and the post-treatment control of HIV need further investigations.

174

175 *Replication-competent virus:* The fraction of cells harboring replication-competent virus can be measured
176 by several assays, mainly the Quantitative Viral Outgrowth Assay (QVOA) and its derivatives [3, 52]. It
177 is now clear that QVOA underestimates the size of the replication-competent reservoir, as not all intact
178 proviruses can be induced by *ex vivo* stimulation [15]. In addition, QVOAs do not account for the host
179 immunological pressures (such as autologous anti-HIV neutralizing antibodies [53]) that can place
180 selective pressure on the rebounding virus. Indeed, the viruses detected in QVOAs that use cells collected
181 pre-ATI often differ from rebound viruses [54, 55], and QVOA measurements did not associate with
182 TTVR in several studies ([31, 24] and abstract [38]). In addition to QVOAs, the murine Viral Outgrowth
183 Assay (mVOA) can be used to determine the replication competency of HIV proviruses *in vivo*, i.e., in
184 the setting of immunodeficient mice [56, 57]. However, the relationship between this measurement and
185 the time/probability of viral rebound remains unknown. Therefore, and barring significant improvements
186 in these assays, the likelihood of using these measurements to predict TTVR in clinical settings is low.

187

188 *Residual viremia:* The source of residual HIV viremia during ART is unclear, but many assume that it
189 reflects HIV transcription and reactivation in multiple tissue compartments throughout the body. The
190 relationship between levels of residual viremia and TTVR has been recently evaluated in a single report
191 [31], and in this report, residual plasma viremia did not correlate with TTVR. However, levels of residual
192 viremia did associate with a faster TTVR in patients treated at the early stage of HIV infection in a different
193 study (abstract [38]). Beyond residual viremia, a low frequency of virological blips during ART associated
194 with a higher likelihood of achieving a PTC phenotype after ART cessation [44]. This suggests that the
195 dynamics of the systemic viral transcription/reactivation during ART could reflect the size of HIV
196 reservoirs and/or immunological pressures on these reservoirs and that these measures may be pertinent
197 to the likelihood of viral rebound following ART.

198

199 *Clinical factors associated with reservoir size:* Several clinical parameters are likely to influence the HIV
200 reservoir size and the association between this reservoir size and TTVR; these include ART regimen, pre-
201 ART viral load, time from diagnosis to ART initiation, and ART duration. As various studies have
202 assessed slightly different associations, they are discussed separately below. In one study, these clinical
203 parameters were not, on their own, associated with TTVR [31]. However, another study found that a

204 longer duration on ART associated with a greater chance of post-treatment control [44]. This latter
205 observation is compatible with a recent report showing that a longer duration on ART is associated with
206 limited proviral gene expression [43]. In a third study, high pre-ART viral load and slower time to viral
207 suppression were independently associated with a larger HIV reservoir size [58]; thus, these clinical
208 parameters are likely to be informative in predicting viral rebound when combined into a composite
209 biomarker with other virological and host parameters. Finally, early initiation of ART limits the size of
210 HIV reservoirs [59]; however, as this reduced size is not associated, on its own, with a delay in viral
211 rebound, early ART initiation cannot serve as a sole biomarker, though it may be an important component
212 of a composite biomarker [30, 57].

213

214 **III. Host markers of time-to-viral-rebound and post-treatment control of HIV.**

215 The host immune system clearly exerts immunological and inflammatory pressure on viral reservoirs both
216 before and after ATI. Historically, such host pressures have been given less consideration as biomarkers
217 of TTVR and post-treatment control than have features of the virus itself. This lack of consideration could
218 explain why some of the above-mentioned virological measurements fail or have been inconsistent in
219 predicting viral rebound after ART. As will be discussed below, identifying host biomarkers could be
220 critical for predicting the duration of viral rebound/remission. In this section, we review the host
221 immunological and inflammatory measures that have been suggested to associate with the TTVR or the
222 probability of viral rebound/remission after ART interruption.

223

224 *Innate immune pressures:* During acute viral infections, the production of type I interferons (IFNs) is an
225 essential host defense mechanism. However, during chronic viral infections, the prolonged and sustained
226 exposure to IFNs can drive a chronic inflammatory state that is detrimental to immunological functions
227 [60-62]. Recently, several studies have linked type I interferon responses pre-ATI to HIV rebound after
228 ATI. First, Gondim et al. [63] found that HIV isolates obtained after ATI are highly resistant to the
229 antiviral activities of type I IFNs, suggesting that innate immune responses (in particular, IFN-mediated
230 responses) might limit the replication of IFN-sensitive viruses during ATI. Second, Zacharopoulou et al.
231 [64] identified specific IFN-associated genes whose increased expression in CD4⁺ T cells was associated
232 with a delayed TTVR and a higher likelihood of PTC phenotype in HIV-infected ART-suppressed women.
233 This observation further supports the notion that IFN-associated innate immune functions impose
234 pressures on the rebounded viruses following ATI. Finally, Mitchell et al. [65] found that plasmacytoid
235 dendritic cells (pDCs) can sense the rebounded viruses after ATI, and that the loss of type I IFN gene
236 expression in these pDCs after ATI would indicate a longer time to viral detection. Together, these studies

237 suggest that the host innate immune response exerts complex pressures on viral rebound after ATI.
238 Therefore, examining type I IFN responses (systemically or in certain cells or tissues) as well as the
239 phenotypes and functions of innate immune cells (such as natural killer cells and myeloid cells) is likely
240 to be critical for understanding innate immune pressures and predicting their impact on viral rebound.

241
242 *Cellular adaptive immune pressures:* The role of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells in post-treatment viral remission
243 is not clear. Studies supporting an association between CD8⁺ T cell functions and post-treatment control
244 include: a study showing that the likelihood of achieving post-treatment control is associated with
245 increased CD8⁺ T cell proliferative responses to HIV Gag and Pol stimulation [28], and a case study in
246 which antiviral CD8⁺ T cell activities associated with post-ART control of HIV [66]. However, no
247 association between CD8⁺ T cell functions and post-ART control was reported by several other studies
248 [26, 11, 67, 28]. Testing for CD4⁺ T cell associations, one study found that PTCs had a slightly higher
249 CD4 cell count at the time of interrupting ART compared to non-controllers [44]. Other characteristics of
250 T cells have been evaluated for their association with TTVR, such as the expression of exhaustion markers
251 on CD4⁺ T cells. The expression levels of several exhaustion markers on CD4⁺ T cells, measured pre-
252 ART, correlated with time-to-rebound [68]. However, the levels of these markers, measured during ART,
253 did not predict viral rebound [68]. CD8 depletion in ART-treated macaques infected with simian
254 immunodeficiency virus (SIV) or ART-treated humanized mice infected with HIV enhances viral
255 reactivation [69], suggesting an important role of these cells in viral reactivation from latency. However,
256 whether any T cell function or characteristic (in humans) can be measured during ART and consistently
257 associate with the likelihood of viral control after ATI is yet to be determined, and this question warrants
258 further investigation.

259
260 *Humoral adaptive immune pressures:* Levels of anti-HIV antibodies can reflect both the degree of HIV
261 persistence and low-level viral replication during ART [70-72]. Therefore, several studies have examined
262 the relationship between the levels, characteristics, and functions of anti-HIV-specific antibodies during
263 ART and viral control after ART. It has been shown that having high levels of anti-HIV antibodies with
264 neutralizing capacity against autologous virus is associated with post-ART viral control [28, 66]. This is
265 consistent with the observation that autologous anti-HIV neutralizing antibodies can limit viral outgrowth
266 in culture [53]. Other features of antibodies may influence their ability to exert immune pressure on the
267 HIV reservoir. Offersen et al. found that the glycosylation of HIV-specific antibodies (in particular,
268 galactosylation) is significantly associated with TTVR in several independent cohorts of ATI [73].
269 Glycosylation can alter the antibody capacity to elicit Fc-mediated innate immune functions such as

270 antibody-dependent complement deposition (ADCD), antibody-dependent cellular phagocytosis (ADCP),
271 and antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity (ADCC) [74-77]. The importance of these Fc-
272 mediated effector functions of antibodies in controlling HIV infection has been highlighted in several
273 studies [78-81]. Therefore, the association between anti-HIV-specific glycosylation and viral rebound may
274 reflect an antibody-mediated immune pressure on the reactivated virus after ATI. Understanding the links
275 between viral rebound and anti-HIV specific antibody titers, function, and characteristics (in the plasma
276 and other body fluids such as cerebrospinal fluid) could be critical not only for developing biomarkers of
277 TTVR but also for advancing our knowledge of antibody-mediated pressures on HIV persistence. This
278 knowledge can serve as a foundation for novel HIV curative strategies and/or as an approach to improve
279 existing strategies. For example, this knowledge could advise how to optimize the glycosylation pattern,
280 thereby the Fc-mediated effector functions, of HIV broadly neutralizing antibodies that are currently being
281 investigated to cure HIV.

282

283 *Genetic and epigenetic modulators of host immune functions:* Some of the above-mentioned
284 immunological functions could be modulated by host genetic or epigenetic factors. Indeed, genome-wide
285 association analyses suggest that specific host genetic variants (including those linked to immune
286 functions) correlate with the size and the transcriptional activity of HIV during ART [82, 83]. However,
287 whether any of these genetic variants can predict viral rebound after ART discontinuation is not clear.
288 Recently, DNA methylation analysis of CD4⁺ T cells showed an association between specific DNA
289 methylation sites and TTVR. These DNA methylation sites occur at genes previously linked to HIV
290 replication and/or immune modulation [84]. It is not clear whether other epigenetic mechanisms (such as
291 histone modifications) are also associated with TTVR. These potential genetic and epigenetic modulators
292 of immune functions may contribute to the overall immune pressure on HIV reservoirs after ART
293 cessation; therefore, they might be useful biomarkers for the viral rebound and targets for potential
294 interventions.

295

296 *Soluble regulators of inflammation and immune functions:* Chronic inflammation is a hallmark of HIV
297 infection, even after ART suppression [85]. Such inflammation is associated with and may directly
298 contribute to the increased rates of aging-associated comorbidities in HIV-infected individuals [86].
299 Chronic inflammation likely involves multifactorial mechanisms, not all of which are well-characterized
300 [87-90]. Sources of chronic inflammation in HIV-infected individuals include ongoing HIV production,
301 cytomegalovirus infection, loss of regulatory T cells, and gut microbial translocation [91-93]. The degree
302 and type of chronic inflammation may be important for viral control before, during-, and after ATI as it

303 may condition the host environment with inflammatory molecules that can indirectly impact upon
304 immunological functions and viral reactivation. However, it is not yet clear whether the pre-ATI levels of
305 any of the classical markers of systemic inflammation can predict viral rebound after ART discontinuation.
306 Such markers would include cytokines and chemokines (such as IFNs, IL-6, TNF- α , IL-1 β),
307 immunoregulatory circulating lectins (such as Galectin-1, Galectin-3, and Galectin-9), complement
308 proteins, or markers of microbial translocation (such as lipopolysaccharide, β -glucan, sCD14, and
309 sCD163). Investigating these markers could be useful, as they are readily accessible and able to shed light
310 on the interplay between chronic inflammation and HIV persistence [94, 95].

311 Beyond the classical markers and drivers of systemic inflammation, several classes of circulating
312 molecules have recently emerged as novel drivers of inflammation and immune functions; these include
313 circulating *metabolites*, *lipids*, and *glycans*. These molecules enter the circulation through active secretion
314 or leakage from multiple tissues, and their levels and chemical characteristics can reflect the inflammatory
315 status of tissues in which HIV persists [96-99]. In addition, these molecules are biologically active. They
316 bind to their receptors on the surface of several immune cells to initiate signal transduction cascades that
317 impact cellular functions. Therefore, these molecules are both accessible markers of inflammation in
318 tissues and drivers of both inflammation and immunological functions, making them an excellent
319 candidate for functional biomarkers discovery (**Figure 1**).

320 a. *Plasma metabolites*. Recent reports suggest that a major determinant of cellular functions that enable
321 or hinder HIV persistence is cellular metabolic processes [100-106] [ENREF 12](#). Certain
322 metabolites, especially tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle metabolites, can influence epigenetic events
323 such as chromatin modifications and DNA methylation [107, 108]. For example, α -ketoglutarate
324 alters the post-translational modification of histones to impact T cell differentiation and myeloid
325 inflammation [109, 106, 107]. Recently metabolomics analyses were performed on plasma samples
326 from a cohort of 24 HIV-infected, ART-suppressed individuals who had participated in an open-
327 ended ATI study without concurrent interventions [25]. This analysis identified specific metabolites
328 whose pre-ATI levels are associated with TTVR and which are also known to impact inflammatory
329 responses. In the same study, the plasma metabolome of a separate cohort of 74 HIV-infected, ART-
330 suppressed individuals who underwent ATI during several AIDS Clinical Trials Group (ACTG)
331 clinical trials was also examined. This cohort contained 27 PTCs. The analysis of these samples
332 showed that a set of metabolites could predict time-to-viral-rebound and probability-of-viral-
333 rebound, even after adjusting for several potential demographic and clinical confounders.

334 Among the plasma metabolites associated with delayed viral rebound are L-glutamic acid and α -
335 ketoglutarate. L-glutamic acid precursor (glutamine) is considered the ‘fuel for the immune system
336 [110-112]’ and plays important roles in regulating immune functions. L-glutamic acid, through its
337 conversion to α -ketoglutarate, can fuel the TCA cycle/oxidative phosphorylation. TCA cycle
338 metabolites may regulate immune processes through epigenetic modifications such as histone
339 modifications [107]; these may impact upon proviral reactivation directly or indirectly by
340 modulating the expression of host genes relevant to HIV transcription. α -ketoglutarate can also
341 inhibit myeloid inflammation through epigenetic reprogramming [106]. This raises the possibility
342 that L-glutamic acid also modulates HIV transcription by regulating myeloid
343 inflammation/activation, which thus conditions the host environment with cytokines/chemokines
344 and other soluble factors that impact T cell functions and processes.

345 Among the plasma metabolites associated with accelerated viral rebound are metabolites linked to
346 gut microbial dysbiosis, such as the pro-inflammatory trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO) [25, 113]
347 and several metabolites within the tryptophan catabolism pathway [25]. The tryptophan catabolism
348 pathway has been associated with gut microbial dysbiosis during HIV infection [114] and the
349 disruption in this pathway has been associated with the development of several aging- and
350 inflammation-associated diseases during HIV infection [115-119]. These data highlight the
351 possibility that gut microbiome-related host pathways contribute to both the development of
352 inflammation-associated co-morbidities and viral persistence during HIV infection [120].
353 Understanding these relationships during ART and post-ATI can provide accessible biomarkers of
354 HIV rebound and can also shed light on novel host pressures on the HIV reservoirs during and after
355 ART cessation.

356 b. *Plasma lipids*. Similar to metabolites, lipids are biologically active molecules involved in a broad
357 range of cellular processes and immunological functions [121]. [ENREF 10](#) For example,
358 lysophospholipids can promote immune inflammation [122-124] and reactivate dormant cancer cells
359 [125]; their levels pre-ATI predicted an accelerated HIV rebound after ART cessation [113]. Such
360 results support the concept that this class of immunological modulators might serve not only as
361 biomarkers of tissue inflammation but also might play an active role in viral reactivation, cellular
362 processes, and immunological functions during or after ATI by conditioning the host environment
363 with higher levels of inflammation.

364 c. *Plasma glycans*. Glycans on circulating glycoproteins and antibodies (e.g., bulk IgGs and IgAs) are
365 essential for regulating several immunological responses [126]. [ENREF 104](#) A number of studies

366 have linked bulk IgG glycosylation to systemic inflammatory responses [127-129]. For example,
367 recent studies have revealed that the potent anti-inflammatory effect of intravenous immunoglobulin,
368 used for rheumatoid arthritis and other inflammatory conditions, is driven by sialic acid-containing
369 *N*-linked glycans on these IgGs [130, 128]. De-sialylating the IgGs reduced their anti-inflammatory
370 functions [131, 127-129, 126]. In addition, several large glycomics studies in the general population
371 revealed that changes in IgG glycosylation (mainly loss of galactose and sialic acid) are closely
372 linked to biological age; these glycomic traits are better predictors of chronological and biological
373 age than other markers such as telomere length [132-134]. [ENREF 99](#) Several glycomic structures
374 on plasma glycoproteins (including bulk IgG) whose levels before an ATI predict both the TTVR
375 and the viral load set-point after the ATI have been recently identified [135, 25]. These potential
376 biomarkers could reflect the biological age and inflammatory status of tissues from which these
377 glycoproteins are shed; however, their association with TTVR could also reflect inflammatory
378 responses mediated by these glycans.

379

380 **IV. Conclusions**

381 It is unlikely that a single marker can predict with certainty the complicated virological milestones of time
382 to viral rebound and/or the probability of HIV rebound after ART cessation. A high likelihood of achieving
383 ART-free viral remission is likely a combination of: 1) a small HIV reservoir, which may be achieved
384 with early ART initiation [59]; 2) an accumulation of non-inducible HIV proviral DNA, for example,
385 proviral DNA that is integrated into centromeric satellite regions (abstract [42]), which may be achieved
386 with a long duration on ART [43]; and 3) host immune pressure on these reservoirs, which may be
387 achieved via one or more of the routes described above. These pressures likely differ among individuals
388 who can achieve post-ATI control of HIV, as recently suggested [66]. Therefore, developing pre-ATI
389 biomarkers of TTVR and PTC phenotype is likely to require not only combining multiple viral and host
390 biomarkers but also the option for personalized medicine approaches.

391

392 The lack of consistency of the above-mentioned proposed biomarkers to predict viral rebound might be
393 due to inconsistencies in how clinical trials defined TTVR or PTC as well as to differences in how the
394 biomarkers were assayed. In addition, very little attention has been paid to cofounders that might impact
395 upon the predictions, including demographics (e.g., ethnicity and age) and clinical features (e.g., time to
396 ART initiation, ART duration, ART regimen, pre-ART viral load, and nadir CD4 counts). One important
397 confounder is sex, especially with recent evidence that sex hormones might influence levels of HIV

398 persistence and latent HIV transcription [136-138]. Thus, the field needs to arrive at a consensus on how
399 to define TTVR and PTC phenotype, and at a set of minimal standards by which measures of each
400 proposed biomarker of TTVR can be assessed and reported. Key demographic and clinical confounders
401 that may impact upon the size of HIV reservoirs and/or the immunological pressures on these reservoirs
402 should become part of standard analysis.

403

404 In this review, we have summarized the virological and host measures that either have been associated
405 with TTVR or the size of HIV reservoirs or that have a high likelihood of exhibiting an association.
406 However, other virological and host measures remain to be explored. For example, *in situ* hybridization-
407 based assays, such as HIV-DNAscope and HIV-RNAscope, can be effective in detecting the presence or
408 absence of HIV DNA and RNA in tissue samples before ART cessation [139-141]. The lack of detectable
409 HIV DNA and RNA in some individuals may provide an additional rationale to stop ART in these
410 individuals. In addition, other host factors such as the quantity and cargo of extracellular vesicles [142],
411 levels and characteristics of cell-free DNA [143], and circulating proteins [144] have been used as
412 biomarkers in other diseases, and might now also be explored as potential makers of viral rebound after
413 ART discontinuation. In summary, developing an approach that combines multiple viral and host
414 biomarkers to predict TTVR and PTC phenotype after ATI is likely necessary. Such an approach will not
415 only mitigate some of the risks associated with ATIs but also provide critical insights into the host
416 immunological and inflammatory pressures on HIV reservoirs. Together, these can significantly accelerate
417 the pace of research toward and the development of an HIV cure.

418 **Figure legends:**

419

420 **Table 1. Viral measurements and their relationship to viral rebound and post-treatment control of**
421 **HIV.**

422

423 **Figure 1. Plasma metabolites, lipids, and glycans are emerging classes of molecules that can be**
424 **makers and drivers of inflammation and immunological functions.** Beyond classical markers and
425 drivers of systemic inflammation, several classes of molecules have recently emerged as potential drivers
426 of inflammation and immunological functions, such as circulating metabolites, lipids, and glycans. These
427 molecules enter the circulation via active secretion or leakage from multiple tissues, and their levels and
428 chemical characteristics can reflect the inflammatory status of these source tissues. In addition, these
429 molecules are biologically active and can bind to their receptors on the surface of several immune cells to
430 initiate a signal transduction cascades that can impact the functions of these cells. Therefore, these
431 molecules are accessible biomarkers of inflammation in tissues as well as drivers of inflammation and
432 immunological functions, making them excellent candidates for functional biomarker discovery.

433 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:**

434 MA-M and L.B.G conceived, designed, and wrote the review.

435

436 **COMPETING INTERESTS STATEMENT**

437 Authors have no competing interests.

438

439 **HUMAN AND ANIMAL RIGHTS AND INFORMED CONSENT**

440 This article does not contain any studies with human or animal subjects performed by any authors.

Table 1: Viral measurements and their relationships to viral rebound and post-treatment control of HIV.

Measurement	Description	Associate with time-to-viral-rebound?	Associate with post-treatment control phenotype?
Proviral HIV DNA measurements			
HIV DNA	Levels of HIV DNA (total, integrated, and/or circular) in the absence of <i>ex vivo</i> stimulation. These measurements overestimate the size of the HIV reservoir as they do not distinguish between defective, transcription-competent, translation-competent, or replication-competent reservoirs [145-147].	<p>Yes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA measured in CD4⁺ T cells from early/acutely treated individuals correlated with time to >400 copies/ml viral load but not >50 copies/ml viral load [12]. - Pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA measured in CD4⁺ T cells from chronically treated individuals correlated with time to >200 copies/ml viral load [24]. - Pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA measured in PBMCs correlated with time to ≥1000 copies/ml viral load or two consecutive times of ≥ 1000 copies/ml viral load [25]. <p>No:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-ATI levels of integrated HIV DNA measured in CD4⁺ T cells from early/acutely treated individuals did not correlate with time to >400 copies/ml viral load [12]. - Pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA measured in CD4⁺ T cells from early/acutely treated individuals did not correlate with time to >20 copies/ml viral load [30]. 	<p>Yes:</p> <p>Low pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA in PBMCs of early or chronically treated individuals associated with post-ART HIV control [26, 11, 27, 25, 28, 29].</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-ATI levels of total HIV DNA measured in PBMCs did not correlate with time to viral rebound.[31-33] 	
Proviral sequencing	Determine levels of genetically intact proviruses (with and without integration sites determination) [15, 34, 148, 45].	Yes: Lower levels of defective and hyper-mutated HIV DNA, but not intact HIV DNA, in PBMCs were associated with a delayed viral rebound (≥ 1000 copies/ml viral load or two consecutive times of ≥ 1000 copies/ml viral load) [25].	Yes: Lower levels of intact, defective, and hyper-mutated HIV DNA measured in PBMCs associated with post-ART HIV control [29, 25].
Intact proviral DNA by IPDA	Levels of intact versus defective proviral HIV DNA. This measurement can underestimate the levels of intact HIV DNA as it is prone to sequence polymorphisms [23].	Yes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower pre-ATI levels of intact proviral DNA, measured by IPDA from PBMCs, predicted delayed viral rebound (≥ 50 copies/ml) at the end of vesatolimod treatment [37]. - Levels of pre-ATI intact HIV DNA, measured by IPDA, predicted TTVR in patients treated during the chronic stage of HIV infection (abstract [38]) 	Yes: PTCs have lower levels of intact HIV DNA, measured by IPDA, compared to NCs (abstract [39]).
HIV proviral integration site analysis	Chromosomal sites and epigenetic features of integrated HIV proviruses [149, 150, 45, 151, 152, 40-43].	To be determined	The integration of intact HIV proviral DNA into centromeric satellite regions may be associated with the post-ART control of HIV (abstract [42]).
HIV RNA and protein measurements			
Cell-associated HIV RNA	Levels of HIV transcripts in the absence of <i>ex vivo</i> stimulation. These measurements overestimate the size of the HIV reservoir as they do not	Yes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher pre-ATI levels of cell-associated unspliced HIV RNA, measured in PBMCs, associated with a shorter time-to-viral rebound (≥ 200 	Yes: Lower levels of unspliced and multisplliced HIV RNA in PBMCs

	distinguish between defective, translation-competent, or replication-competent reservoirs [153-155, 47, 10, 156].	<p>copies/ml viral load, ≥ 1000 copies/ml viral load, or two consecutive times of ≥ 1000 copies/ml viral load) [10, 25].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher pre-ATI levels of cell-associated unspliced HIV RNA, but not multi-spliced HIV RNA, measured in PBMCs in early-treated individuals, associated with shorter time-to-viral rebound (≥ 50 copies/ml viral load or ≥ 400 copies/ml viral load) [33]. <p>No:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-ATI levels of total HIV RNA measured in CD4⁺ T cells from chronically treated individuals did not correlate with time to >200 copies/ml viral load [24]. - Pre-ATI levels of unspliced HIV RNA measured in PBMCs did not correlate with time to viral rebound [31]. 	associated with post-ART HIV control [28, 25].
Induction-based viral RNA reactivation	The frequency of cells harboring <i>ex vivo</i> inducible HIV transcripts (transcriptional competent reservoir). These measurements do not distinguish between defective or replication-competent reservoirs [157, 46].	<p>No:</p> <p>Time to viral rebound was not associated with <i>in vitro</i> viral release [31].</p>	To be determined
Cell-associated p24 protein quantification	Levels of HIV p24 expression (translation-competent reservoir; with and without <i>ex vivo</i> stimulation). These measurements can overestimate the size of HIV reservoir as the replication-competent reservoir is just a fraction of the	<p>Yes:</p> <p>Higher pre-ATI levels of <i>ex vivo</i> inducible HIV p24 correlated with a delayed viral rebound during peg-IFNα-2b monotherapy (abstract [51]).</p>	To be determined

	translation-competent reservoir [158].		
Replication-competent virus measurements			
Viral Outgrowth (QVOA and its derivatives)	The frequency of cells infected with replication-competent HIV that can produce infectious virus upon <i>ex vivo</i> stimulation. These assays underestimate the size of replication-competent reservoir as they rely on the efficiency of the <i>ex vivo</i> stimulation step [3, 1, 15, 159, 160, 157, 161, 162].	No: QVOA measurement did not associate with time-viral-rebound [31, 24].	To be determined
Other measurements			
Residual viremia.	Levels of HIV particles in the plasma (or other body fluids) during ART [163].	Yes: Levels of residual viremia associated with a faster TTVR in patients treated at the early stage of HIV infection in a recent study (abstract [38]) No: Residual viremia did not correlate with time-to-viral-rebound [31].	Yes: a low frequency of virological blips during ART, was associated with a higher likelihood to achieve a PTC phenotype after ART cessation [44].

Figure 1

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